

Accepted Manuscript

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PII: S0956-7135(18)30043-4

DOI: [10.1016/j.foodcont.2018.01.031](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2018.01.031)

Reference: JFCO 5962

To appear in: *Food Control*

Received Date: 12 December 2017

Revised Date: 29 January 2018

Accepted Date: 30 January 2018

Please cite this article as: Ríos-Reina Rocí., García-González D.L., Callejón Raquel.Mari. & Amigo José.Manuel., NIR spectroscopy and chemometrics for the typification of Spanish wine vinegars with a protected designation of origin, *Food Control* (2018), doi: 10.1016/j.foodcont.2018.01.031.

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**NIR SPECTROSCOPY AND CHEMOMETRICS FOR THE TYPIIFICATION OF
SPANISH WINE VINEGARS WITH A PROTECTED DESIGNATION OF ORIGIN**

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2 Abstract

3 High-quality wine vinegars protected by the indication “Protected Designation of Origin”
4 (PDO) need efficient tools to protect their brands and prevent adulteration and unfair
5 competition. In this sense, Near-Infrared spectroscopy (NIRs) combined with chemometrics has
6 demonstrated its usefulness in food authentication. This work assessed NIRs and Chemometrics
7 as a rapid and non-destructive methodology for this purpose. In this study, 83 high-quality wine
8 vinegars of the Spanish PDOs “*Vinagre de Jerez*”, “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” and
9 “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” of different categories, and 11 wine vinegars without PDO, were
10 analyzed in the range 12000-4000 cm^{-1} . Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed to
11 explore the spectra and Partial Least Squares-Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) was used to
12 build classification models. The high ability of prediction obtained (>90% correct classification)
13 demonstrated the usefulness of this methodology for authentication of PDO wine vinegars and
14 their categories.

15

16 **Keywords:** Wine vinegar; Protected Designation of Origin; Near-Infrared spectroscopy;
17 Principal component analysis; Partial Least Squares-Discriminant Analysis.

18

19 1. INTRODUCTION

20 Wine vinegar has become a highly appreciated food product in gastronomy and one of the
21 most consumed types of vinegar in Europe (Paneque, Morales, Burgos, Ponce, & Callejón,
22 2017). Some wine vinegars, traditionally linked to a specific geographical area, have their
23 specifications related to their chemical and sensory features controlled by European regulations
24 under a legislative system named “Protected Designation of Origin” (PDO) (Chinnici et al.,
25 2009). Thus, as occurring with other food, such as extra virgin olive oil, wine vinegars with a
26 PDO are recognized as a food product with the highest quality. In this field, Spain is one of the
27 major producers of high-quality wine vinegars, producing three of the five types of PDO
28 vinegars in Europe (Council Regulation (EC) No 510/2006): “*Vinagre de Jerez*”, “*Vinagre de*
29 *Condado de Huelva*” and “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*”. These vinegars are made under
30 traditional processed and from high quality wines protected by their corresponding PDO.
31 Furthermore, some of these PDO wine vinegars are subjected to a period of aging in wooden
32 butts causing chemical modifications in their composition (Morales, Tesfaye, García-Parrilla,
33 Casas, & Troncoso, 2002). According to the sweetness, time and system of aging (“*criaderas*
34 *and solera*” or “*añada*” systems), different categories are considered within each Spanish PDO
35 (Table 1) having singular and specific characteristics (Council Regulation (EC) No 510/2006).

36 Due to the demand of high-quality vinegars has significantly increased over the last years,
37 and in addition to food quality is directly related to commercial value, there are suspicious that
38 adulteration and unfair competition in the vinegar industry is being practiced (Consonni,
39 Cagliani, Rinaldini, & Incerti, 2008; Sáiz-Abajo, González-Sáiz, & Pizarro, 2004; Tesfaye,
40 Morales, García-Parrilla, & Troncoso, 2002b). For this reason, wineries and regulatory councils
41 are demanding effective analytical tools to allow rapid and inexpensive analysis to verify the
42 origin of the vinegars in order to protect their brands and to prevent from adulteration. Some of
43 the classical analytical methods suggested for assessing food quality and differentiating
44 geographical origins such as gas-chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) (Callejón,
45 Morales, Silva Ferreira, & Troncoso, 2008), atomic absorption spectrometry or high-

46 performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) (Tesfaye, Morales, García-Parrilla, & Troncoso,
47 2002a), are based on the measurement of the chemical compounds presented in vinegar (e.g.
48 volatiles and phenolic compounds or metals). Although these methods provide high quality
49 information, they require sample pretreatment steps, and they are destructive, time-consuming
50 and expensive. For this reason, there is a growing interest in developing rapid, accurate,
51 inexpensive and non-destructive methodologies based on non-targeted techniques for
52 characterization and authentication of high-quality vinegars (Callejón et al., 2012; De la Haba,
53 Arias, Ramírez, López, & Sánchez, 2014; Fan et al., 2011). In this sense, vibrational
54 spectroscopic techniques, such as Near Infrared spectroscopy (NIRs) and Fourier Transform
55 mid infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) have demonstrated to meet these characteristics being
56 informative at molecular level and very useful for identification and verification of raw
57 materials and final products, producing a single spectral fingerprint of each matrix, and
58 moreover, enable the direct measurement of wine vinegar samples with minimum or no sample
59 preparation (Lohumi, Lee, Lee, & Cho, 2015). Thus, a previous study of the characterization of
60 Spanish PDO wine vinegars by FTIR spectroscopy equipped with an attenuated total reflectance
61 accessory (ATR) (Ríos-Reina, Callejón, Oliver-Pozo, Amigo, & García-González, 2017b)
62 demonstrated the usefulness of this technique in the control of the different categories described
63 in wine vinegar PDOs. This method was applied at first due to it provides a greater amount of
64 chemical information compared to NIR spectroscopy in terms of chemical assignment of
65 observances and allows the interpretation of the spectra without the need of complex
66 chemometrics. Nevertheless, although a direct identification of the compounds is difficult by
67 NIRs, this methodology is extremely useful for highlighting groups of compounds that have
68 more relevance, giving a fingerprint of each sample, as well as it is faster, easier to implement
69 and easy to use (Baeten & Dardenne, 2002; Karoui & De Baerdemaeker, 2007; Stuart, 2004).
70 For all these reasons, NIRs could be a good alternative to be applied and its performance in
71 high-quality wine vinegars authentication must be checked.

72 However, the fact that the differences between the NIR spectra of different compounds are
73 usually very subtle, and the spectral occurrences in the NIR region are commonly dominated by
74 overtones, combination absorption bands and normally possess broad overlapping, makes
75 necessary the use of chemometrics. Thus, the information provided by NIRs requires advanced
76 multivariate data analysis (such as principal component analysis ‘PCA’, classification methods
77 as partial least squares-discriminant analysis ‘PLS-DA’, soft independent modelling by class
78 analogy ‘SIMCA’, etc.) to allow an efficient treating and interpreting of the signals, as well as
79 to perform a discrimination, classification and authentication of samples. In this context, in the
80 last few years, the use of NIRs in combination with multivariate chemometric analysis has been
81 widely reviewed for many different approaches such as authentication, detecting adulteration or
82 differentiating geographical origins of food products (Cozzolino, 2014; Grassi, Amigo,
83 Lyndgaard, Foschino, & Casiraghi, 2014; Pillonel et al., 2003; Alamprese, Amigo, Casiraghi, &
84 Engelsen, 2016; Liu et al., 2008). However, with regard to the classification of vinegars by
85 NIRs, there are only a few papers related to wine vinegars and high-quality wine vinegars,
86 pointing out the utility of this spectroscopic technique in relation to other food commodities
87 (Casale, Sáiz Abajo, González Sáiz, Pizarro, & Forina, 2006; Fan et al., 2011; Zhao, Zhang,
88 Zhao, Zhang, & Liu, 2011). Furthermore, despite the advantages of NIRs and FTIR vibrational
89 spectroscopic techniques are well known nowadays, the implementation of one of these
90 techniques in the characterization and classification of these high-quality wine vinegars still
91 requires to be further studied, comparing their suitability in the analysis of this food matrix. For
92 these reasons, the aim of the study is to investigate the potential and suitability of NIRs in
93 conjunction with multivariate classification tools as a rapid, inexpensive and non-destructive
94 methodology for the characterization and authentication of the three Spanish wine vinegar
95 PDOs (“*Vinagre de Jerez*”, “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” and “*Vinagre de Montilla-*
96 *Moriles*”), assessing its ability to classify PDO wine vinegars according to their category and to
97 discriminate them from commercial wine vinegars without PDO.

98

99 2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

100 2.1 Samples

101 2.1.1 PDO wine vinegars

102 Eighty-three wine vinegar samples belonging to the three Spanish PDOs were analyzed
103 in this study: 41 samples from “*Vinagre de Jerez*”, 29 from “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*”,
104 and 13 from “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*”. These samples were provided by the Regulatory
105 Councils of each Spanish PDO, which assessed and certified the authenticity of the wine
106 vinegars. The less number of samples collected for the PDO “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*”, as
107 well as the lack of “*Gran Reserva*” samples, is explained by the fact that it has been recently
108 registered with the indication of PDO (registered in 2015). Furthermore, a different number of
109 samples within each PDO were collected for the established categories (aged and sweet) due to
110 the rate of production of each category during last years (2014-2015). More information about
111 samples included in the study is shown in Table 1.

112 2.1.2 Commercial wine vinegar samples without PDO

113 A total amount of 11 wine vinegars from different regions were purchased in local markets
114 and wineries and named in the study as “Commercial samples without PDO” (V): 7 samples
115 produced in northern Spain; 1 wine vinegar from the same region as “*Vinagre de Montilla-*
116 *Moriles*” PDO but without the PDO indication; and 3 samples without specification of the
117 geographical origin. The number of samples was inevitably limited by their production and
118 availability. Therefore, the work was developed under a feasibility point of view and the
119 production and occurrence in the market was take into account for the construction of the
120 models.

121 2.2 NIR measurements

122 NIR spectra were collected in absorption mode using an ABB Bomen IR spectrometer (Q-
123 interline, X, Denmark), equipped with a 1 mm path length cuvette. Spectral data were collected
124 in the range of 12000–4000 cm^{-1} , with a resolution of 8 cm^{-1} and 64 scans for both backgrounds
125 and samples. Wine vinegar samples were directly analyzed without sample pre-treatment by

126 pipetting them into 1 mL shell vial, 40x80 mm transparent (Skandinaviska Genetec AB, Lund,
127 Sweden) before measurement. The spectrometer was interfaced to a computer with
128 GRAMS/AI™ Spectroscopy Software (Thermo Fisher Scientific software) for spectral
129 acquisition and exportation. The spectrum of each sample was obtained in triplicate in a random
130 sequence at room temperature (21–23 °C).

131 **2.3 Data processing and multivariate analysis**

132 Data analysis was performed by using PLS_Toolbox 7.9.5 (Eigenvector Research Inc.,
133 Wenatchee, WA) working under MATLAB v.8.5.0 environment (The Mathworks Inc., Natick,
134 MA). Different preprocessing methods were studied prior to multivariate data analysis. The best
135 pre-processing method was smoothing (SMT) 7 point and second order filtering operation, to
136 reduce random noise and standard normal variate (SNV) method (Barnes, Dhanoa, & Lister,
137 1989) to correct for baseline variations due to the different scattering of the samples. Moreover,
138 mean centering (MC) was performed on the spectra. Two segments of the spectrum were
139 removed from the whole wavenumber range of the spectra: the first one because of the low
140 value of the signal/noise and the second one because of the strong combination band of O-H
141 from water (4000-5430 cm^{-1} and 7200-6400 cm^{-1} , respectively). The corrected NIR spectra
142 before and after preprocessing are shown on Fig. I (Supplementary Material).

143 Before classification models, an exploratory analysis of the data is advisable to be
144 performed to detect outliers, recognize patterns in samples distribution and relationships
145 between variables and classes. For this purpose, PCA was carried out prior to any classification
146 approach. After the PCA models, full cross validation (leave-one-out) was used as validation
147 method for the PLS-DA models. Several PLS-DA models were built with different
148 classification purposes: the first one, classifying the different commercialized categories (aged
149 and sweet) within the same PDO, and the second purpose was to differentiate wine vinegars
150 with PDO from those without PDO certification. The models were tested using a data set that
151 was not used in the process of calibration model building. The samples belonging to each
152 dataset were randomly selected by the Kennard-Stone algorithm (Kennard & Stone, 1969) and

153 split into training and test sets (Table I Supplementary Material), making sure that in both
154 datasets at least one sample of each category or class was included (with the corresponding
155 replicates). The first dataset (training set) was composed by 75% of the samples (in triplicate) to
156 perform a calibration and internal validation of the models. The other dataset (test set) was
157 composed by 25% of total samples to evaluate the discriminative power of the models. Test
158 samples were only used in the final stage to evaluate the true predictive ability of the calibrated
159 model. The ability of classification of PLS-DA was assessed by statistical parameters as
160 sensitivity, specificity and classification error of calibration (CAL), cross-validation (CV) and
161 prediction (PRED). The correct number of latent variables (LV) was chosen taking into account
162 the root mean square error of calibration (RMSEC) and leave-one-out cross-validation
163 (RMSECV), selecting the number of LVs that led to a minimum of both parameters.

164

165 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

166 NIR spectra of the wine vinegar samples are shown (Fig. IA Supplementary Material) as
167 well as the pre-processed spectra (Fig. IB Supplementary Material). In both cases, the
168 differences between categories or PDOs are not easily observed and further data processing is
169 required. Therefore, PCA was used to explore the spectra. This procedure also allows detecting
170 any grouping of samples. The number of principal components (PCs) was selected according to
171 their explained variance.

172 3.1 Exploratory analysis of Spanish PDO wine vinegars

173 3.1.1 “*Vinagre de Jerez*” PDO

174 Two principal components (PCs) were extracted in the PCA model of “*Vinagre de Jerez*”
175 PDO. Fig.1 shows the score and loading plots obtained of the first two PCs (PC1 and PC2) that
176 explained an accumulative explained variance of 81.21%.

177 On one hand, Fig. 1.A shows that PC1 and PC2 allowed the discrimination between the
178 aging categories, placing samples of less aged vinegars (“*Crianza*” >6 months aged) in the
179 positive side of PC1 and PC2, and placing samples of the most aged category (“*Reserva*” and
180 “*Gran Reserva*”) in the negative side of PC1 and PC2. However, some overlapping was also
181 observed between samples belonging to “*Crianza*” (from 6 months to 2 years aged) and
182 “*Reserva*” (more than 2 years aged) categories due to the proximity between their ranges of
183 aging and the fact that time is a continuous variable. Thus, “*Reserva*” vinegars with more years
184 of aging are more similar to vinegars from “*Gran Reserva*” category, and vinegars with only
185 two years of aging are closer to “*Crianza*” vinegars that have to be aged for at least 6 month. In
186 the same way, there was a sample belonging to “*Reserva*” category placed near “*Gran Reserva*”
187 samples (category aged for at least 10 years) that seemed to have an aging longer than the rest of
188 “*Reserva*” wine vinegar samples. There was also a clearly differentiation of the sweet category
189 (“*Pedro Ximenez*”) from the rest of the samples. A previous analysis of these PDO wine
190 vinegars by middle infrared and multivariate fluorescence spectroscopy showed similar results

191 (Ríos-Reina, et al., 2017a; Ríos-Reina, Callejón, Oliver-Pozo, Amigo, & García-González,
192 2017b).

193 On the other hand, 6 wine vinegars belonging to the “*Vinagre de Jerez*” PDO (4 “*Crianza*”
194 and 2 “*Reserva*”) were purchased from the market (named “M”) instead of collected from the
195 wineries by the regulatory councils (named “W”), and they were included in the PCA model to
196 assess whether they would comply with the requirements and characteristics controlled under
197 the PDO according to their spectral features. The second figure (Fig. 1.B) shows that these
198 samples were placed with the rest of the PDO wine vinegars collected from wineries. The
199 observed similarity between these two groups might indicate that their characteristics and
200 quality were in agreement with the PDO regulations. However, it could be observed that one
201 “*Reserva*” sample (showed in the figure in triplicate) was grouped with samples belonging to
202 the immediately before aged category “*Crianza*” instead of with their labeled category, which
203 could indicate a mislabeled sample that aged for a shorter time than the period regulated for a
204 “*Reserva*” category. This result may indicate that NIR could be subjected to another study with
205 the specific objective of labelling verification.

206 In regards to the loadings (Fig 1.C), the main absorption bands involved in chemical
207 variation during aging, and also related to sweet category, were those from 5200 to 6500 cm^{-1} .
208 These bands have been previously assigned to the presence of water, which shows an intense
209 absorption at $\sim 6860 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\sim 1450 \text{ nm}$) related to the first O-H overtone of both water and ethanol
210 (Osborne, Fearn, & Hindle, 1993), and in the region of 5300-5000 cm^{-1} ($\sim 1900\text{-}1950 \text{ nm}$),
211 related to the combination of stretching and deformation of the O-H group in water. The
212 absorption bands around 6000 cm^{-1} ($\sim 1690 \text{ nm}$) might be related to the $-\text{CH}_3$ stretching first
213 overtone or C-H groups of chemical compounds that suffer changes during aging, widely
214 described in literature (Callejón, Torija, Mas, Morales, & Troncoso, 2010; García-Parrilla,
215 Heredia, & Troncoso, 1999; Tesfaye, Morales, Benítez, García-Parrilla, & Troncoso, 2004).
216 These absorption bands could be associated to aromatic compounds (Cozzolino, Smyth, &
217 Gishen, 2003; Yu, Fu, Xie, Ying, & Zhou, 2007) which have been found to increase their

218 concentration during aging together with the increasing of phenolic compounds released by
219 wood barrels and oxidation products derived from chemical reactions (Callejón et al., 2008;
220 Morales et al., 2002). Moreover, the absorption band at $\sim 5600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\sim 1790\text{ nm}$), which is also
221 relevant and related to O-H bonds, has been associated with sucrose, fructose and glucose in
222 fruit juices (Giangiacomo & Dull, 1986). Those compounds are present in high concentration in
223 “*Pedro Ximenez*” vinegars due to the fact that they are produced by the addition of “*Pedro*
224 *Ximenez*” Sherry wine, which has a high concentration of grape sugars. All these particular
225 characteristics reflected by the spectra provide the chance to discriminate the different
226 commercialized “*Vinagre de Jerez*” PDO categories.

227 3.1.2 “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” PDO

228 Fig.2 shows the results obtained by carrying out a PCA with wine vinegars belonging to
229 “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” PDO. Firstly, a PCA was carried out with the total of the
230 “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” samples (Fig. 2.A). The scores plot of the first two PCs
231 (explaining 92.95% of total variance) allowed a separation of samples according to the aging
232 time with a trend of placing from less aged vinegars (SC and SO) in the negative side of PC1 to
233 the most aged vinegars (RE and AN) in the positive side of PC1 and PC2. It could be observed
234 that 12 wine vinegars collected from two specific wineries (marked with circles) were placed in
235 the most positive side of PC1 and they seemed not to follow the general trend of the PCA model
236 according to the aging time. The analysis was repeated to verify that these samples were not
237 spectral outliers. Moreover, when a PCA model was developed only with these 12 wine
238 vinegars, the aging effect was also observed in the same way (Fig. 2.B), placing the most aged
239 samples in the positive side of PC1. The difference of these wine vinegars will probably be a
240 special characteristic of their raw material (i.e. produced by a different wine or from different
241 grape varieties, but always from the allowed ones in this PDO). To study these samples in
242 depth, more accurate analytical techniques (e.g. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance, mass
243 spectrometry, etc.) will be applied.

244 Once these samples were studied separately, they were removed from the global model and
245 a PCA was again performed to better explore the total dataset (Fig. 2.C). The scores plot of the
246 first two PCs allowed the separation of samples according to the aging time (explaining 94.87%
247 of total variance). The intense wavelength region of PC2 had an important role in the
248 discrimination of wine vinegars without aging (SC) and the immediately aged category
249 “*Solera*” (SO) aged for at least 6 months and PC1 showed a clear differentiation between the
250 less aged categories (SC and SO) with less than 2 years of aging, and the most aged categories
251 “*Reserva*” and “*Añada*” (RE and AN) with more than 2 and 3 years of aging, respectively.
252 Results also showed that aging system was also an important difference: “*Añada*” category is
253 obtained by a static aging whereas “*Reserva*” wine vinegars are obtained by the traditional
254 method named “*criaderas y solera*” where vinegars are aged in different butts and they are
255 sequentially mixed. Finally, the scores plot showed two “*Reserva*” wine vinegars placed next to
256 the “*Solera*” samples. This behavior could be explained as these samples were probably aged
257 during the minimum time allowed for the “*Reserva*” category (2 years) and therefore, their
258 characteristics were similar to the most aged “*Solera*” wine vinegars (between 6 months and 2
259 years of aging).

260 Regarding the loading plot of PC1 and PC2 (Fig. 2.D) for the last PCA model, the region of
261 the spectra that showed the highest relevance in this model (5200-6200 cm^{-1}) agreed with those
262 observed in the developed “*Vinagre de Jerez*” PCA model. Once again, the absorption band at
263 $\sim 5200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ of PC1, previously assigned to the absorption bands of water, explained the
264 distinction of the least aged vinegars whereas the bands located between 5800 and 6200 cm^{-1}
265 explained the separation of the most aged samples. This observation was partially explained by
266 the evaporation process that occurs during aging. Thus, less aged wine vinegars contain more
267 water in the composition since water evaporates during the aging process (Callejón et al., 2010;
268 Tesfaye et al., 2002). This phenomenon gives rise to an increase in the concentration of the rest
269 of compounds (e.g. phenolic and aromatic compounds) whose absorption bands are mainly
270 associated to the bands located between 5800 and 6200 cm^{-1} .

271 3.1.3 “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” PDO

272 A PCA model was carried out to explore the data and to detect grouping and outliers in
273 “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” PDO samples (Fig. 3). Despite the low number of samples, the
274 first two PCs also seemed to allow the differentiation of the categories according to aging like
275 the models obtained with the other two PDOs (Fig. 3.A). Moreover, “*Pedro Ximenez*” wine
276 vinegar category was again clearly differentiated from the rest of samples by the spectral
277 wavelengths of PC1 (96.83% of total variance). The loading plot showed again the importance
278 of the bands associated to water (at 5200 cm^{-1}) as well as the region where sugars absorb (5600
279 cm^{-1}), possibly related to the special composition of “*Pedro Ximenez*” vinegars. Thus, “*Vinagre*
280 *de Montilla-Moriles Pedro Ximenez*” is produced by adding must of raisins (dried grapes) of the
281 “*Pedro Ximenez*” variety during the production process (Council Regulation (EC) No
282 510/2006), increasing the concentration of sugars in the vinegar and other compounds such as
283 brown pigments produced by Maillard reaction of the carbohydrates and free amino acids
284 (Casale et al., 2006). In the case of “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” PDO, the reducing sugar
285 content must be at least 70g/L (Council Regulation (EC) No 510/2006.). However, as the
286 production of “*Pedro Ximenez*” category in the other commercialized PDO “*Vinagre de Jerez*”
287 is different, the final composition may be also quite different. Thus, in the case of “*Vinagre de*
288 *Jerez*” PDO, sweet vinegars are produced by the addition of “*Pedro Ximenez*” Sherry wine,
289 which entails a content of at least 60 g/L of reducing material from this wine (Council
290 Regulation (EC) No 510/2006). This difference was also observed by developing a PCA model
291 with “*Pedro Ximenez*” samples from both PDOs (Fig. 3.C-D), in which samples from “*Vinagre*
292 *de Jerez*” and “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” were placed separately.

293 3.1.4. Wine vinegar samples without PDO

294 In order to corroborate the ability of the developed methodology in the authentication of PDO
295 wine vinegars with respect to non-PDO wine vinegars, some samples without a PDO indication
296 (V) were included in the models together with the wine vinegars of each PDO (“*Vinagre de*
297 *Jerez*” “J”, “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” “C” and “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” “M”). As

298 a first step, different PCA models were built (Fig. II Supplementary Material). The score plots
299 showed a clear difference between the PDO wine vinegars and the group of vinegars without
300 PDO. Only the visual differentiation between some “*Pedro Ximenez*” samples belonging to
301 “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” PDO (MPX) and one “*Pedro Ximenez*” wine vinegar without
302 PDO (VPX) was not perfectly clear (Fig. II C.1 Supplementary Material). However, a “*Pedro*
303 *Ximenez*” sample without PDO that was produced in the same geographical area as “*Vinagre de*
304 *Montilla-Moriles*” PDO (VMPX) was placed in the scores plot extremely separated from
305 “*Pedro Ximenez*” vinegars within the PDO (MPX). These results reaffirms the unique quality
306 and characteristics of wine vinegars produced under the specifications of a PDO due to major
307 controls and their traditional method of production that provided high-quality conditions to
308 vinegars since a very long period of time is required. No use of NIRs technology on the
309 differentiation of PDO wine vinegars from vinegars without the PDO indication has been
310 reported to date.

311 Regarding loadings plot (Fig. II A.2, B.2, C.2 Supplementary Material), the first two
312 PCs, which explained between 94% and 99% of total variance in the three PCA models, pointed
313 out that the spectral regions mainly responsible of the differentiation were again those between
314 5000-6500 cm^{-1} together with the region between $\sim 10000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 12000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ that had an
315 important relevance in this particular case.

316 **3.2. PLS-DA classification models**

317 After a preliminary exploratory analysis of spectra by PCA, PLS-DA model was developed
318 for a classification purpose. The first PLS-DA models were developed to classify samples
319 between their established PDO categories (henceforth “*category classification*”). The second
320 PLS-DA models were developed to confirm the ability of NIRs to authenticate and differentiate
321 PDO wine vinegars from wine vinegars without the PDO designation (henceforth “*PDO/origin*
322 *classification*”). Categories with lower number of samples were not included in the models.
323 Moreover, “*Añada*” category was grouped with “*Reserva*” category in “*Vinagre de Condado*
324 *de Huelva*” PDO, as the aging time regulated in each one was similar (more than two-three

325 years of aging), differing only on the aging system used. The models were tested by dividing the
326 total number of samples in two sets (training and test sets). Further information about the
327 number of samples used for modeling and predicting are shown in Table I Supplementary
328 Material.

329 *3.2.1. PLS-DA models for distinguishing the three aged categories within each PDO*
330 *(category classification)*

331 The statistical parameters obtained by PLS-DA in the different models are shown in Table
332 2a. High sensitivity and specificity values (%) were obtained in the PLS-DA models for each
333 category. The 87-100% of the samples were correctly classified, demonstrating that all the
334 categories within each PDO could be successfully separated from the rest of classes. These
335 results confirmed and improved those obtained in a previous study of the authors (Ríos-Reina et
336 al., 2017a), in which these vinegars were analyzed by multidimensional fluorescence
337 spectroscopy coupled with different classification tools, resulting in the need of using a non-
338 linear classification tool (support vector machines) to obtain good classification results. In the
339 case of NIRs, a linear classification approach is enough for obtaining good results. However, the
340 results also showed that the categories that showed lowest classification rates were those that
341 would be in the boundaries between categories according to their aging period (“*Solera*” for
342 “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” PDO and “*Reserva*” in the other two PDOs). These results
343 were acceptable considering the high variability of these samples due to the factor that they
344 were aged over a wide range of time that is reflected over their complex chemical composition
345 (García-Parrilla et al., 1999). These intermediate categories were expected to be
346 spectroscopically and chemically similar to the vinegars of the immediately previous or
347 following category. Furthermore, the highly variability in the intermediate categories was also
348 observed by Callejón et al., (2012), whose study revealed that the lowest classification rates
349 were obtained for the intermediate aged category “*Reserva*”, with an aging time between
350 “*Crianza*” and “*Gran Reserva*” categories.

378 techniques were examined by comparing the percentage of correct predictions (Table 3). For
379 this comparison, PLS-DA classification models were built with ATR-FTIR data obtained in a
380 previous research carried out by the authors of this study (Ríos-Reina, Callejón, Oliver-Pozo,
381 Amigo, & García-González, 2017b). In this model, the range between 1500 and 900 cm^{-1} was
382 included in the PLS-DA, due to the fact that, as it was previously reported, it showed the main
383 spectral bands assigned to complex interacting vibrations related to the unique fingerprint of
384 each vinegar.

385 NIR classification models showed percentages of correct predictions in the range 86.7-
386 100% in most of the categories while in the case of ATR-FTIR the percentage of correct
387 prediction were 58.4-100% (Table 3). In most of the cases, the classification rates were higher
388 in NIRs compared to ATR-FTIR. However, it is important to consider the advantages of both
389 techniques. Thus, ATR-FTIR spectroscopy has the advantages of being able to determine
390 absorption bands with clear chemical assignments, which facilitates the interpretation of the
391 spectra. Although NIR spectra are more difficult to interpret and the calibration procedures were
392 more complicated, it also shows an easy and robust analysis and yielded satisfactory
393 classification results for PDO wine vinegars. Depending on the classification purpose
394 (categories and PDO vs non-PDO) and the needs for interpreting the spectra, one of both
395 techniques could be proposed to be applied in quality control of vinegars, or even the
396 combination of both of them.

397

398 4. Conclusions

399 In this work, the combination of NIR with chemometrics has demonstrated to be useful
400 for a rapid characterization and classification of the Spanish PDO wine vinegars and for
401 controlling the authenticity of their commercialized categories (aged and sweet). A simple
402 exploration of the NIR data by a PCA pointed out some that aging and the protection under a
403 PDO had an effect in the spectra, showing similarities between the spectra of the aged
404 categories of the three Spanish PDOs. The absorption bands most involved in aging changes,
405 and also related to sweet category, were those from ~ 5200 to ~ 6500 cm^{-1} , associated to the
406 presence of water and aromatic and phenolic compounds that have shown changes during aging.
407 Furthermore, the sweet category “*Pedro Ximenez*” showed some characteristic bands at the
408 same region (~ 5600 cm^{-1}) mainly associated to sugars, due to their special characteristic of
409 production. The unique characteristics of the Spanish PDO wine vinegars, which directly affect
410 to the NIR spectra, allowed a satisfactory classification according to the category (aged and
411 sweet categories within each PDO) and PDOs versus non-PDO differentiation (PDO wine
412 vinegars from vinegars without this quality indication) by the development of PLS-DA
413 classification models with the NIR spectrum of samples.

414 The advantages of this methodology would allow implementing it as an alternative tool
415 for fingerprinting wine vinegar samples on a large scale, this analytical tool being cost-effective
416 and rapid. Further research will be carried out to test this technique at industrial scale with a
417 higher number of samples to evaluate the efficiency in real authentication problems.

418 5. Acknowledgements

419 The authors would like to thank the Spanish Regulatory Councils of the wine vinegars
420 PDOs for their invaluable help with the acquisition of the samples for the study. Authors also
421 thank University of Copenhagen, specifically to Professor Franciscus Winfried J van der Berg
422 and the department of food science for providing the equipment and their knowledge in the
423 methodology. This work was supported by “*Consejería de Economía, Innovación y Ciencia*” of

424 “Junta de Andalucía” [P12-AGR-1601], and “Ministerio de Educación Cultura y Deporte”
425 (MECD, Spanish Government) for the FPU pre-doctoral fellowship [grant number
426 FPU2014/01247].

427

428 6. References

429 Alamprese, C., Amigo, J. M., Casiraghi, E., & Engelsen, S. B. (2016). Identification and
430 quantification of turkey meat adulteration in fresh, frozen-thawed and cooked minced beef
431 by FT-NIR spectroscopy and chemometrics. *Meat Science*, *121*, 175–181.
432 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2016.06.018>

433 Baeten, V., & Dardenne, P. (2002). Spectroscopy: Developments in instrumentation and
434 analysis. *Grasas Y Aceites*, *53*(1), 45–63. <http://doi.org/10.3989/gya.2002.v53.i1.289>

435 Barnes, R. J., Dhanoa, M. S., & Lister, S. J. (1989). Standard Normal Variate Transformation
436 and De-trending of Near-Infrared Diffuse Reflectance Spectra. *Applied Spectroscopy*, *43*,
437 772–777.

438 Callejón, R. M., Amigo, J. M., Pairo, E., Garmón, S., Ocaña, J. A., & Morales, M. L. (2012).
439 Classification of Sherry vinegars by combining multidimensional fluorescence, parafac
440 and different classification approaches. *Talanta*, *88*, 456–462.
441 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2011.11.014>

442 Callejón, R. M., Morales, M. L., Silva Ferreira, A. C., & Troncoso, A. M. (2008). Defining the
443 typical aroma of Sherry vinegar: Sensory and chemical approach. *Journal of Agricultural
444 and Food Chemistry*, *56*(17), 8086–8095. <http://doi.org/10.1021/jf800903n>

445 Callejón, R. M., Torija, M. J., Mas, A., Morales, M. L., & Troncoso, A. M. (2010). Changes of
446 volatile compounds in wine vinegars during their elaboration in barrels made from
447 different woods. *Food Chemistry*, *120*, 561–571.

448 Casale, M., Sáiz Abajo, M. J., González Sáiz, J. M., Pizarro, C., & Forina, M. (2006). Study of

- 449 the aging and oxidation processes of vinegar samples from different origins during storage
450 by near-infrared spectroscopy. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 557(1–2), 360–366.
451 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2005.10.063>
- 452 Chinnici, F., Guerrero, E. D., Sonni, F., Natali, N., Marín, R. N., & Riponi, C. (2009). Gas
453 chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) characterization of volatile compounds in
454 quality vinegars with protected European geographical indication. *Journal of Agricultural
455 and Food Chemistry*, 57(11), 4784–4792. <http://doi.org/10.1021/jf804005w>
- 456 Consonni, R., Cagliani, L. R., Rinaldini, S., & Incerti, A. (2008). Analytical method for
457 authentication of Traditional Balsamic Vinegar of Modena. *Talanta*, 75(3), 765–769.
458 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2007.12.005>
- 459 Council Regulation (EC) No 510/2006 of 20 March 2006 on the protection of geographical
460 indications and designations of origin for agricultural products and foodstuffs. [http://eur-](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32006R0510)
461 [lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32006R0510](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32006R0510). Accessed 15 March
462 2016.
- 463 Cozzolino, D. (2014). An overview of the use of infrared spectroscopy and chemometrics in
464 authenticity and traceability of cereals. *Food Research International*, 60, 262–265.
465 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2013.08.034>
- 466 Cozzolino, D., Smyth, H. E., & Gishen, M. (2003). Feasibility Study on the Use of Visible and
467 Near-Infrared Spectroscopy Together with Chemometrics to Discriminate between
468 Commercial White Wines of Different Varietal Origins. *Journal of Agricultural and Food
469 Chemistry*, 51(26), 7703–7708. <http://doi.org/10.1021/jf034959s>
- 470 De la Haba, M. J., Arias, M., Ramírez, P., López, M. I., & Sánchez, M. T. (2014).
471 Characterizing and authenticating montilla-moriles PDO vinegars using near infrared
472 reflectance spectroscopy (nirs) technology. *Sensors (Switzerland)*, 14(2), 3528–3542.
473 <http://doi.org/10.3390/s140203528>

- 474 Fan, W., Li, H., Shan, Y., Lv, H., Zhang, H., & Liang, Y. (2011). Classification of vinegar
475 samples based on near infrared spectroscopy combined with wavelength selection.
476 *Analytical Methods*, 3(8), 1872. <http://doi.org/10.1039/c1ay05101f>
- 477 García-Parrilla, M. C., Heredia, F. J., & Troncoso, A. M. (1999). Sherry wine vinegars:
478 Phenolic composition changes during aging. *Food Research International*, 32(6), 433–
479 440. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-9969\(99\)00105-2](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-9969(99)00105-2)
- 480 Giangiacomo, R., & Dull, G. G. (1986). Near Infrared Spectrophotometric Determination of
481 Individual Sugars in Aqueous Mixtures. *Journal of Food Science*, 51(3), 679–683.
482 <http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2621.1986.tb13910.x>
- 483 Grassi, S., Amigo, J. M., Lyndgaard, C. B., Foschino, R., & Casiraghi, E. (2014). Beer
484 fermentation: Monitoring of process parameters by FT-NIR and multivariate data analysis.
485 *Food Chemistry*, 155, 279–286. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2014.01.060>
- 486 Karoui, R., & De Baerdemaeker, J. (2007). A review of the analytical methods coupled with
487 chemometric tools for the determination of the quality and identity of dairy products. *Food*
488 *Chemistry*, 102(3), 621–640. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2006.05.042>
- 489 Kennard, R.W. and Stone, L.A. (1969) Computer-aided Design of Experiments. *Technometrics*,
490 11, 137-148. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00401706.1969.10490666>
- 491 Liu, L., Cozzolino, D., Cynkar, W. U., Damberg, R. G., Janik, L., O'Neill, B. K., Colby, C. B.,
492 Gishen, M. (2008). Preliminary study on the application of visible-near infrared
493 spectroscopy and chemometrics to classify Riesling wines from different countries. *Food*
494 *Chemistry*, 106(2), 781–786. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2007.06.015>
- 495 Lohumi, S., Lee, S., Lee, H., & Cho, B. K. (2015). A review of vibrational spectroscopic
496 techniques for the detection of food authenticity and adulteration. *Trends in Food Science*
497 *and Technology*, 46(1), 85–98. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2015.08.003>
- 498 Morales, M. L., Tesfaye, W., García-Parrilla, M. C., Casas, J. A., & Troncoso, A. M. (2002).

- 499 Evolution of the aroma profile of sherry wine vinegars during an experimental aging in
500 wood. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 50(11), 3173–8.
501 <http://doi.org/10.1021/jf011313w>
- 502 Osborne, B., Fearn, T., & Hindle, P. (1993). *Practical NIR spectroscopy with applications in*
503 *food and beverage analysis*. (A.-W. Longman, Ed.) ((2nd ed.)). Ltd: Harlow UK.
- 504 Paneque, P., Morales, M. L., Burgos, P., Ponce, L., & Callejón, R. M. (2017). Elemental
505 characterisation of Andalusian wine vinegars with protected designation of origin by ICP-
506 OES and chemometric approach. *Food Control*, 75, 203–210.
507 <http://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2016.12.006>
- 508 Pillonel, L., Luginbühl, W., Picque, D., Schaller, E., Tabacchi, R., & Bosset, J. O. (2003).
509 Analytical methods for the determination of the geographic origin of Emmental cheese:
510 Mid- and near-infrared spectroscopy. *European Food Research and Technology*, 216(2),
511 174–178. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-002-0628-5>
- 512 Ríos-Reina, R., Callejón, R. M., Oliver-Pozo, C., Amigo, J. M., & García-González, D. L.
513 (2017b). ATR-FTIR as a potential tool for controlling high quality vinegar categories.
514 *Food Control*, 78, 230–237. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2017.02.065>
- 515 Ríos-Reina, R., Elcoroaristizabal, S., Ocaña-González, J. A., García-González, D. L., Amigo, J.
516 M., & Callejón, R. M. (2017a). Characterization and authentication of Spanish PDO wine
517 vinegars using multidimensional fluorescence and chemometrics. *Food Chemistry*, 230,
518 108–116. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2017.02.118>
- 519 Sáiz-Abajo, M. J., González-Sáiz, J. M., & Pizarro, C. (2004). Classification of wine and
520 alcohol vinegar samples based on near-infrared spectroscopy. Feasibility study on the
521 detection of adulterated vinegar samples. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*,
522 52(25), 7711–7719. <http://doi.org/10.1021/jf049098h>
- 523 Stuart, B. H. (2004). *Infrared Spectroscopy: Fundamentals and Applications. Methods* (Vol. 8).

- 524 John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <http://doi.org/10.1002/0470011149>
- 525 Tesfaye, W., Morales, M. L., Benítez, B., García-Parrilla, M. C., & Troncoso, a. M. (2004).
526 Evolution of wine vinegar composition during accelerated aging with oak chips. *Analytica*
527 *Chimica Acta*, 513(1), 239–245. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2003.11.079>
- 528 Tesfaye, W., Morales, M. L., García-Parrilla, M. C., & Troncoso, A. M. (2002a). Evolution of
529 phenolic compounds during an experimental aging in wood of Sherry vinegar. *Journal of*
530 *Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 50(24), 7053–7061. <http://doi.org/10.1021/jf020602x>
- 531 Tesfaye, W., Morales, M. L., García-Parrilla, M. C., & Troncoso, A. M. (2002b). Wine vinegar:
532 Technology, authenticity and quality evaluation. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*,
533 13(1), 12–21. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2244\(02\)00023-7](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2244(02)00023-7)
- 534 Yu, H., Fu, X., Xie, L., Ying, Y., & Zhou, Y. (2007). Discrimination between Chinese rice
535 wines of different geographical origins by NIRS and AAS. *European Food Research and*
536 *Technology*, 225(3–4), 313–320. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-006-0416-8>
- 537 Zhao, Y., Zhang, S., Zhao, H., Zhang, H., & Liu, Z. (2011). Fast discrimination of mature
538 vinegar varieties with Visible-NIR spectroscopy. *IFIP Advances in Information and*
539 *Communication Technology*, 344 AICT(PART 1), 721–728. [http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-](http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-18333-1_87)
540 [642-18333-1_87](http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-18333-1_87).
- 541

542 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

543 **Figure 1.** Results of principal component analysis carried out with NIR spectral data of
544 “*Vinagre de Jerez*” wine vinegars. The scores plots with the representation of the categories (**A**)
545 and with the representation of the provenance of samples (**B**) are shown as well as the
546 corresponding loadings of the first two principal components (PC1 and PC2) (**C**). The acronyms
547 for the different vinegar categories are defined in Table 1.

548 **Figure 2.** Results of principal component analysis carried out with NIR spectral data of
549 “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” wine vinegars. The scores plot of the first principal
550 components obtained with the total of wine vinegars is shown (**A**), as well as the results
551 obtained with only the samples from two specific wineries (**B**) and the scores and loadings plots
552 (**C and D**) after removing the samples from these two specific wineries. The acronyms for the
553 different vinegar categories are defined in Table 1.

554 **Figure 3.** Results of principal component analysis carried out with NIR spectral data of
555 “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” samples. The scores and loadings plots of the first two principal
556 components (PC1 and PC2) are shown (**A and B**), as well as the results of principal component
557 analysis (scores and loadings plots) of the first two principal components (PC1 and PC2) carried
558 out with “*Pedro Ximenez*” wine vinegar samples (**C and D**). The acronyms for the different
559 wine vinegar categories and PDOs are defined in Table 1.

560

561 TABLES

Table 1. PDO and “non-PDO commercial” wine vinegars included in the study

Wine vinegars with PDO	PDO	Category	Aging time	Code	n	Wineries
	“Vinagre de Jerez” (J)	<i>Crianza</i>	>6 months	JCR	15+4	34
		<i>Reserva</i>	>2years	JRE	15+2	
		<i>Gran Reserva</i>	>10 years	JGR	2	
<i>Pedro Ximenez</i>		--	JPX	3		
Total					41	
“Vinagre de Condado de Huelva” (C)	<i>Sin crianza</i>	0 months	CSC	8	8	
	<i>Solera</i>	>6months	CSO	9		
	<i>Reserva</i>	>2years	CRE	8		
	<i>Añada</i>	>3years	CAN	4		
	Total					29
“Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles” (M)	<i>Crianza</i>	>6 months	MCR	4	8	
	<i>Reserva</i>	>2years	MRE	4		
	<i>Pedro Ximenez</i>	--	MPX	5		
	Total					13
	Wine vinegars without PDO					
Origin characteristics	Category	Code		n	Markets	
Notern Spain (<i>Catalonia, La Rioja, Galicia</i>)	<i>Crianza, Reserva and Pedro Ximenez</i> categories	VN		7	4	
Similar geographical area than “ <i>Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles</i> ” PDO		VMPX		1		
No aged	Unknown origin	V		3	3	
Total				11		

Table 2. Sensitivity, specificity and classification errors (%) obtained for (a) PLS-DA classification models corresponding to the vinegar category of each Spanish PDO; (b) PLS-DA classification models to differentiate PDO wine vinegars from external vinegars. The acronyms for the different vinegar categories are defined in Table 1.

<i>(a) "Category classification"</i>									
Spanish PDOs	<i>"Vinagre de Jerez"</i>			<i>"Vinagre de Condado de Huelva"</i>			<i>"Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles"</i>		
N° LVs	6			2			5		
Category	JCR	JRE	JPX	CSC	CSO	CRE-CAN	MCR	MRE	MPX
Sensitivity CAL	94.4	88.6	100.0	100.0	93.3	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Sensitivity CV	94.4	85.7	100.0	100.0	93.3	100.0	88.9	88.9	100.0
Sensitivity PRED	100.0	88.9	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Specificity CAL	97.6	88.1	98.6	97.4	82.4	100.0	100.0	95.2	100.0
Specificity CV	95.1	83.3	95.8	100.0	93.3	100.0	100.0	85.7	100.0
Specificity PRED	83.3	100.0	100.0	100.0	73.3	91.7	100.0	100.0	100.0
Class. Error CAL	3.9	11.6	0.7	1.3	12.1	0.0	0.0	2.3	0.0
Class. Error CV	5.2	15.5	2.1	1.3	12.1	0.0	5.5	12.6	0.0
Class. Error PRED	8.3	5.5	0.0	0.0	13.3	4.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
<i>(b) "PDO/origin classification"</i>									
	<i>"Vinagre de Jerez" PDO</i>	Wine vinegars without PDO	<i>"Vinagre de Condado de Huelva" PDO</i>	Wine vinegars without PDO	<i>"Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles" PDO</i>	Wine vinegars without PDO			
N° LVs	3		4		3				
Sensitivity CAL	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0			
Sensitivity CV	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	95.8			
Sensitivity PRED	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0			
Specificity CAL	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0			
Specificity CV	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	95.8	100.0			
Specificity PRED	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0			
Class. Error CAL	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0			
Class. Error CV	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.1	2.1			
Class. Error PRED	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0			

Table 3. Comparison of PLS-DA models obtained for the classification of wine vinegar samples according to the commercialized category within each PDO. The percentage of correct predictions correspond to models tested with independent data sets.

<i>PLS-DA Classification of categories within each PDO (category classification)</i>			
Spectroscopic technique	NIR	FTIR	
Spectral region used	12000-7200 cm ⁻¹ and 6400-5430 cm ⁻¹	1500-900 cm ⁻¹	
N° variables included	1450	310	
Pre-processing technique	SMT + SNV	-	
PLS-DA model of “Vinagre de Jerez” PDO	LVs	6	4
	Correct prediction of categories (%)	JCR: 91.7 JRE: 94.5 JPX: 100.0	JCR: 83.75 JRE: 70.6 JPX: 100.0
PLS-DA model of “Vinagre de Condado de Huelva” PDO	LVs	2	2
	Correct prediction of categories (%)	CSC: 100.0 CSO: 86.7 CRE-AN: 95.9	CSC: 70.0 CSO: 81.7 CRE-AN: 80.0
PLS-DA model of “Vinagre de Montilla- Moriles” PDO	LVs	5	5
	Correct prediction of categories (%)	MCR: 100.0 MRE: 100.0 MPX: 100.0	MCR: 91.7 MRE: 58.4 MPX: 100.0

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

562 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

563 **Figure I.** NIRs spectra (with section spectra removed) of all PDO wine vinegars included in the
564 study before (raw spectra) **(A)** and after preprocessing (smoothing and SNV) **(B)**. Note: C=
565 “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*”, J= “*Vinagre de Jerez*”, “M”= “*Vinagre de Montilla-*
566 *Moriles*”, V= “Wine vinegars without PDO”

567 **Figure II.** Scores plots obtained by principal component analysis carried out with NIR spectra
568 of “*Vinagre de Jerez*” **(A.1)**, “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” **(B.1)**, “*Vinagre de Montilla-*
569 *Moriles*” **(C.1)**, together with wine vinegars without PDO. The loadings plots of the first two
570 principal components (PC1 and PC2) **(A.2, B.2, C.2)** are also shown. Note: C= “*Vinagre de*
571 *Condado de Huelva*”, J= “*Vinagre de Jerez*”, “M”= “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*”, V= “Wine
572 vinegars without PDO”

TABLES

Table I. Number of samples (by triplicate) used in each dataset for developing PLS-DA classification models. The acronyms for the different vinegar categories are defined in Table 1.

Model	Classification of wine vinegar categories within each Spanish PDO											
Spanish PDO	"Vinagre de Jerez"				"Vinagre de Condado de Huelva"				"Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles"			
Category	JCR	JRE	JPX	Total	CSC	CSO	CRE-CAN	Total	MCR	MRE	MPX	Total
Model	36	36	6	78	12	15	18	45	9	9	12	30
Prediction	9	9	3	21	6	6	6	18*	3	3	3	9
Model	Classification of Spanish PDO wine vinegars from wine vinegars without PDO											
Category	"Vinagre de Jerez" PDO vs wine vinegars without PDO			"Vinagre de Condado de Huelva" PDO vs wine vinegars without PDO			"Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles" PDO vs wine vinegars without PDO					
Spanish PDO	J	V	Total	C	V	Total	M	V	Total			
Model**	90/24	21/24	111/48	63/24	21/24	72/48	30/24	24/24	54/48			
Prediction**	30/9	12/9	42/18	24/9	12/9	36/18	9/9	9/9	18/18			

*Note: Samples belonging to the two specific wineries (2SC, 2SO, 2 Re and 2 AN) marked in Figure 3.B were not included in the PLS-DA models. **All the samples included in training and test sets/ balanced number of samples per group included in training and test sets.

Acronyms J= "Vinagre de Jerez"; C= "Vinagre de Condado de Huelva"; M= "Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles"; V= wine vinegars without PDO.

573

574

Highlights

- Near-Infrared spectroscopy was studied for characterizing PDO wine vinegars
- PLS-DA models were able to differentiate the Spanish PDOs and wine vinegar categories
- Wine vinegars without PDO were used to test the models
- NIR provided better classification results than ATR-FTIR analysis
- These techniques, or their combination, could be useful in vinegar quality control